

Testing the Regression Coefficients for the Two Parameter Multicollinear Gaussian Linear Regression Models: An Empirical Comparison

Md Ariful Hoque¹, B. M. Golam Kibria², and Zoran Bursac¹

¹Department of Biostatistics

²Department of Mathematics and Statistics
Florida International University

Abstract

In linear regression analysis, the assumption of independence among explanatory variables is crucial, with the ordinary least squares (OLS) estimator typically regarded as the Best Linear Unbiased Estimator (BLUE). However, multicollinearity poses challenges by distorting the estimation of individual variable effects and impeding reliable statistical inference. To address this issue, various two-parameter estimators have been proposed in the literature. This paper aims to compare the t-test statistics used to assess the significance of regression coefficients when employing two-parameter biased estimators. A Monte Carlo simulation study is conducted to evaluate their performance, focusing on the maintenance of the empirical type I error rate and power properties, in line with standard testing practices. The findings indicate that some two-parameter estimators offer significant power improvements while preserving the nominal 5% significance level.

Keywords: Empirical power; Linear Regression; type I error rate; Multicollinearity; Ridge Regression estimator; Kibria-Lukman estimator; Simulation study.

1. Introduction

In linear regression analysis, the assumption that explanatory variables are mutually independent is fundamental. Under this condition, the ordinary least squares (OLS) estimator is traditionally acknowledged as the Best Linear Unbiased Estimator (BLUE). Also, the presence of multicollinearity introduces significant complications by making it difficult to isolate the contribution of individual regressors. Consequently, OLS estimates may become unstable, yielding large standard errors and wide confidence intervals, ultimately weakening inferential conclusions (Kibria, 2003) [18]. To mitigate these problems, researchers have introduced a variety of alternative biased estimators, each designed to improve efficiency while trading off a small degree of bias. Early pioneering work includes Hoerl and Kennard (1970) [12], followed by developments from Ehsanes Saleh and Kibria (1993) [9], Kibria and Banik (2016) [19], Kibria and Lukman (2020) [21], Hoque and Kibria (2023) [15], Hoque and Kibria (2024) [16], among many others.

Another essential aspect of regression analysis is hypothesis testing, particularly in evaluating whether individual regression coefficients is essential to test. Such tests allow practitioners to determine which predictors meaningfully contribute to the outcome.

The primary aim is to assess the statistical significance of regression coefficients in the presence of multicollinearity through hypothesis testing. While literature in this area exists, it remains relatively limited. For example, Halawa and Bassiouni (2000) [11] were among the first to introduce non-exact t-tests for regression coefficients, with emphasis on empirical type I error rates and statistical power. Later, Cule et al. (2011) [5] investigated hypothesis testing procedures in ridge regression

for both linear and logistic models. Gokpinar and Ebegil (2016) [10] expanded the scope by evaluating t-tests across various ridge parameter estimators. Similarly, Kibria and Banik (2019) [20] and Perez-Melo and Kibria (2020) [28] examined robustness of such tests under different ridge settings. These contributions highlight the importance of continuing to refine and evaluate inferential methods in this context.

Under the Liu regression framework, Ullah et al. (2017) [31] studied hypothesis testing for regression coefficients in this setting, while Perez-Melo et al. (2022) [29] compared Ridge, Liu, and Kibria-Lukman estimators, further broadening the scope of testing methodologies. These studies underscore the relevance of evaluating a wide spectrum of biased estimators to enhance inference under multicollinearity.

The present paper aims to provide a comprehensive comparison of various t-test statistics used for testing different regression coefficients across multiple estimation techniques. Specifically, we evaluate OLS, Yang and Chang (2010) [35] estimator, the Modified Ridge Type (MRT) estimator, and several other two-parameter approaches. Using Monte Carlo simulations, we analyze both type I error control and empirical power, following the methodology of Halawa and Bassiouni (2000) [11] and Gokpinar and Ebegil (2016) [10]. The ultimate goal is to offer practical recommendations regarding which test statistics are most effective in identifying significant predictors when multicollinearity exists, thereby advancing applied regression methodology. A more extensive treatment of this topic, which incorporates additional two-parameter estimators and broader simulation results, can be found in Hoque et al. (2025) [14].

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the statistical methodology, including the regression model and various two parameter biased estimators; Section 3 presents the simulation design and empirical results; and Section 4 concludes with a summary and final remarks.

2. Statistical Methodology

In this section, we will discuss the form of the linear regression model and different type of two parameter estimators.

2.1 Model and Some Existing Estimators

Consider the following multiple linear regression model:

$$Y = X\beta + \epsilon, \quad \epsilon \sim N(0, \sigma^2 I_n), \#(2.1)$$

where Y is a $n \times 1$ vector of responses, X is an $n \times p$ full rank matrix of explanatory variables, β is an $p \times 1$ vector of unknown regression coefficients and ϵ is an $n \times 1$ error vector distributed as normal with $E(\epsilon) = 0$, and $Var(\epsilon) = \sigma^2 I_n$, where I_n is an $n \times n$ identity matrix.

The ordinary least square (OLS) estimator of β in (2.1) is given by.

$$\hat{\beta}_{OLS} = (X^T X)^{-1} X^T Y, \#(2.2)$$

where X is the design matrix.

To test the j th component of β equals zero, the test statistics based on OLS estimator is defined as:

$$H_0: \beta_j = 0 \text{ vs } H_1: \beta_j \neq 0$$

$$t = \frac{\hat{\beta}_j}{SE(\hat{\beta}_j)} \# (2.3)$$

where $\hat{\beta}_j$ is the j th component of $\hat{\beta}$, and $SE(\hat{\beta}_j)$ is the square root of the i th diagonal element of $Var(\beta_{OLS}) = \sigma^2 (X^T X)^{-1}$ where:

$$\hat{\sigma}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{OLS})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{OLS})}{n - p - 1} \# (2.4)$$

Under the null hypothesis, the test statistic in equation (2.3) follows a student's t-distribution with $n - p - 1$ degrees of freedom. When $X^T X$ is poorly conditioned as a result of multicollinearity, the OLS estimator in equation (2.2) becomes unstable and produces inflated variance of estimates. To overcome this problem, Hoerl and Kennard (1970) [12] proposed the Ridge estimator, which adjusts the diagonal elements of $X^T X$ by adding a constant k .

2.2 Two Parameter Estimators

2.2.1 Liu Type Two Parameter Estimator

To address the multicollinearity, Liu (2003) [22] has suggested a two-parameter estimator for linear regression model, defined as

$$\hat{\beta}_{LTE} = (X^T X + kI)^{-1} (X^T Y - d\beta^*) \# (2.5)$$

where β^* is any estimator of β , and we choose $\beta^* = \beta_{OLS}$ and then we can get,

$$\hat{\beta}_{LTE} = (X^T X + kI)^{-1} (X^T X - dI) \hat{\beta}_{OLS}.$$

The expected value and covariance matrix of this estimator are,

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{LTE}) = A_{LTE} \beta,$$

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{LTE}) = \sigma_{LTE}^2 A_{LTE} (X^T X)^{-1} A_{LTE}^T,$$

where $A_{LTE} = (X^T X + kI)^{-1} (X^T X - dI)$, and σ_{LTE}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{LTE}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{LTE})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{LTE})}{n - p - 1} \# (2.6)$$

For choosing k and d in this case from Liu (2003) [22],

$$\hat{k}_{LTE} = \frac{\lambda_1 - 100\lambda_p}{99}, \hat{d}_{LTE} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^p \left(\frac{(\hat{\sigma}^2 - k\alpha_j^2)}{(\lambda_j + \hat{k})^2} \right)}{\sum_{j=1}^p \left(\frac{(\hat{\sigma}^2 + \lambda_j \alpha_j^2)}{\lambda_j (\lambda_j + \hat{k})^2} \right)}.$$

2.2.2 Ozkale and Kaciranlar Two Parameter Estimator

Ozkale and Kaciranlar (2007) [27] introduced another two-parameter estimator, formulated as:

$$\hat{\beta}_{TP} = A_{TP} \hat{\beta}_{OLS} \# (2.7)$$

where $A_{TP} = (X^T X + kI)^{-1} (X^T X + dI)$.

The expected value and covariance structure of $\hat{\beta}_{TP}$ are:

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{TP}) = A_{TP} \beta,$$

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{TP}) = \sigma_{TP}^2 A_{TP} (X^T X)^{-1} A_{TP}^T,$$

and σ_{TP}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{TP}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{TP})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{TP})}{n - p - 1}. \#(2.8)$$

Now, for estimating the unknown k and d , from Ozkale and Kaciranlar (2007) [27], we get the optimal estimator of d for fixed k value as:

$$\hat{d}_{opt} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^p \frac{(k\alpha_j^2 - \hat{\sigma}^2)}{(\lambda_j + k)^2}}{\sum_{j=1}^p \frac{k(\hat{\sigma}^2 + \hat{\alpha}_j \lambda_j)}{\lambda_j (\lambda_j + k)^2}},$$

and

$$\hat{k} = \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{\hat{\alpha}_j^2 - d \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}^2 + \alpha_j^2}{\lambda_j} \right)}.$$

Hoerl et al. (1975) [13] suggested estimating k by taking the harmonic mean of the values that originally proposed by Hoerl and Kennard (1970) [12], whereas Kibria (2003) [18] proposed using the arithmetic means of k values. Thus, we can take arithmetic and harmonic means of k values. Then,

$$\hat{k}_{HM} = \frac{p\hat{\sigma}^2}{\sum_{j=1}^p \left[\hat{\alpha}_j^2 - d \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}^2 + \alpha_j^2}{\lambda_j} \right) \right]} \text{ and } \hat{k}_{AM} = \frac{1}{p} \sum_{j=1}^p \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{\hat{\alpha}_j^2 - d \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}^2 + \alpha_j^2}{\lambda_j} \right)}.$$

It is evident that \hat{d}_{opt} depends on the value of k and the estimators of k also function of d . For this reason, an iterative method is recommended for the use of these parameters. The selection of the parameters d and k can be obtained by using the following iterative scheme.

Step 1. Calculate $\hat{d} = \min \left[\frac{\hat{\alpha}_j^2}{\frac{\hat{\sigma}^2 + \hat{\alpha}_j^2}{\lambda_j}} \right]$.

Step 2. Estimate k_{AM} or k_{HM} by using \hat{d} in Step1.

Step 3. Obtain \hat{d}_{opt} by using the estimators k_{AM} or k_{HM} in Step 2.

Step 4. If \hat{d}_{opt} is negative use $\hat{d}_{opt} = \hat{d}$ because \hat{d} is always less than one and bigger than zero, $0 < \hat{d} < 1$.

2.2.3 New Biased Estimator Based on Ridge

Sakallıoglu and Kaciranlar (2008) [30] proposed a variant of ridge-type estimators, introducing an additional biasing parameter to improve stability. The estimator is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\beta}_{NBE} &= (X^T X + I)^{-1} (X^T y + d\hat{\beta}_{Ridge}) \\ &= (X^T X + I)^{-1} (X^T X + (d+k)I) (X^T X + kI)^{-1} X^T X \hat{\beta}_{OLS}. \#(2.9) \end{aligned}$$

The expected value and covariance matrix are expressed as

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{NBE}) = A_{NBE}\beta,$$

$$\text{Var}(\hat{\beta}_{NBE}) = \sigma_{NBE}^2 A_{NBE} (X^T X)^{-1} A_{NBE}^T,$$

where $A_{NBE} = (X^T X + I)^{-1} (X^T X + (d+k)I) (X^T X + kI)^{-1} X^T X$ and σ_{NBE}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{NBE}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{NBE})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{NBE})}{n-p-1}. \# (2.10)$$

For estimating the unknown parameter k and d , we can choose,

$$\hat{d}_{opt} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^p \frac{\lambda_j(\hat{\alpha}_j^2 - \hat{\sigma}^2)}{(\lambda_{j+1})^2(\lambda_{j+k})}}{\sum_{j=1}^p \frac{\lambda_j(\lambda_j \hat{\alpha}_j^2 + \hat{\sigma}^2)}{(\lambda_{j+1})^2(\lambda_{j+k})^2}}.$$

For fixed k , $k_{HK} = \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{\sum_{j=1}^p \hat{\alpha}_j^2}$ and $k_{HKB} = \frac{p\hat{\sigma}^2}{\sum_{j=1}^p \hat{\alpha}_j^2}$.

2.2.4 Yang and Chang Estimator

Yang and Chang (2010) [35] suggested a flexible two-parameter approach defined as:

$$\hat{\beta}_{YC} = Y_{k,d} \hat{\beta}_{OLS}, \# (2.11)$$

where $Y_{k,d} = (X^T X + I)^{-1} (X^T X + dI) (X^T X + kI)^{-1} (X^T X)$, and k and d are biasing parameters.

The expected value and covariance of $\hat{\beta}_{YC}$ are:

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{YC}) = Y_{k,d} \beta,$$

$$\text{Var}(\hat{\beta}_{YC}) = \sigma_{YC}^2 Y_{k,d} (X^T X)^{-1} Y_{k,d}^T,$$

and σ_{YC}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{YC}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{YC})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{YC})}{n-p-1}. \# (2.12)$$

For k , we fixed d , and based on the Yang and Chang (2010) [35], we get the optimal k as

$$\hat{k}_j = \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2(\lambda_{j+d}) - (1-d)\lambda_j \hat{\alpha}_j^2}{(\lambda_{j+1}) \hat{\alpha}_j^2}.$$

We can apply different formulas for this parameter, such as arithmetic mean, harmonic mean and median.

Then, we get,

$$\hat{d}_{opt} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^p [((k+1)\lambda_{j+k})\lambda_j \hat{\alpha}_j^2 - \lambda_j^2 \hat{\sigma}^2] / [(\lambda_{j+1})^2 (\lambda_{j+k})^2]}{\sum_{i=1}^p (\hat{\sigma}^2 + \lambda_j \hat{\alpha}_j^2) \lambda_j / [(\lambda_{j+1})^2 (\lambda_{j+k})^2]}.$$

The selection of the estimators of the parameters k and d in $\hat{\beta}_{YC}$ is obtained iteratively as follows:

Step 1: Obtain an initial estimate of d using $\hat{d} = \min \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{\hat{\alpha}_j^2} \right)$

Step 2: Obtain \hat{k} using \hat{d} in step 1.

Step 3: Estimate \hat{d}_{opt} using \hat{k} in step 2.

Step 4. If \hat{d}_{opt} is not between $0 < \hat{d}_{opt} < 1$ use $\hat{d}_{opt} = \hat{d}$.

2.2.5 Almost Unbiased Two Parameter Estimator

Wu and Yang (2011) [34] introduced an almost unbiased two-parameter estimator to further reduce bias in multicollinear settings. It is expressed as:

$$\hat{\beta}_{AUTP} = \left[I - k^2(1-d)^2(X^T X + kI)^{-2} \right] \hat{\beta}_{OLS} \# (2.13)$$

The expected value and covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{AUTP}$ are:

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{AUTP}) = A_{AUTP}\beta,$$

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{AUTP}) = \sigma_{AUTP}^2 A_{AUTP} (X^T X)^{-1} A_{AUTP}^T,$$

where $A_{AUTP} = [I - k^2(1-d)^2(X^T X + kI)^{-2}]$,

and σ_{AUTP}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{AUTP}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{AUTP})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{AUTP})}{n-p-1} \# (2.14)$$

$$\text{Now, } d_{jopt} = 1 - \frac{(\lambda_j + k)\sigma}{k} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma^2 + \lambda_j \alpha_j^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \text{ and } k_{jopt} = \frac{\sigma \lambda_j}{(1-d) \sqrt{\sigma^2 + \lambda_j \alpha_j^2 - \sigma}}$$

The selection of the estimators of the parameters k and d can be got by using the following iterative approach.

$$\text{Step 1: Compute } \hat{d} \text{ from } d = 1 - \min \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{\lambda_j \alpha_j^2 + \sigma^2}} \right)$$

Step 2: Obtain \hat{k}_{jopt} using \hat{d} in step 1.

Step 3: Estimate \hat{d}_{jopt} using \hat{k}_{jopt} in step 2.

Step 4. If \hat{d}_{jopt} is negative use $\hat{d}_{jopt} = \hat{d}$ because it is always less than 1 but it may be smaller than 0.

2.2.6 Unbiased Two Parameter Estimator

Wu (2014) [33] proposed an unbiased two parameter estimator and defined as:

$$\hat{\beta}_{UTP} = A_{UTP} \hat{\beta}_{OLS} + (1 - A_{UTP})J \# (2.15)$$

where $A_{UTP} = (X^T X + kI)^{-1} (X^T X + kdI)$ and $J \sim N \left(\beta, \left(\frac{\sigma^2}{k(1-d)} \right) (X^T X + kdI)^{-1} X^T X^{-1} \right)$ for $k > 0, 0 < d < 1$ and the prior information J is a random vector for specified mean and covariance.

The expected value and covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{UTP}$ are:

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{UTP}) = \beta,$$

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{UTP}) = \sigma_{UTP}^2 A_{UTP} (X^T X)^{-1},$$

and σ_{UTP}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{UTP}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{UTP})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{UTP})}{n-p-1} \# (2.16)$$

Now, for fixed k , we can get an unbiased estimator of d as follows:

$$\hat{d} = 1 - \frac{\sigma^2 [p + k \text{tr}(X^T X)^{-1}]}{k(\hat{\beta}_{OLS} - I)(\hat{\beta}_{OLS} - I)^T}$$

where $\text{tr}(X^T X)^{-1} = \sum_{j=1}^p 1/\lambda_j$.

If $k(\hat{\beta}_{OLS} - J)(\hat{\beta}_{OLS} - J)^T - \sigma^2[p + ktr(X^T X)^{-1}] > 0$ then

$$\hat{d}^* = 1 - \frac{\sigma^2[p + ktr(X^T X)^{-1}]}{k(\hat{\beta}_{OLS} - J)(\hat{\beta}_{OLS} - J)^T}.$$

Otherwise $\hat{d}^* = 1$.

And k is defined as:

$$\hat{k} = \frac{p\sigma^2}{(1-d)(\hat{\beta}_{OLS} - J)(\hat{\beta}_{OLS} - J)^T - \sigma^2tr(X^T X)^{-1}}.$$

If $(1-d)(\hat{\beta}_{OLS} - J)(\hat{\beta}_{OLS} - J)^T - \sigma^2tr(X^T X)^{-1} > 0$, then

$$\hat{k}^* = \frac{p\sigma^2}{(1-d)(\hat{\beta}_{OLS} - J)(\hat{\beta}_{OLS} - J)^T - \sigma^2tr(X^T X)^{-1}}.$$

Otherwise

$$\hat{k}^* = \frac{p\sigma^2}{(1-d)(\hat{\beta}_{OLS} - J)(\hat{\beta}_{OLS} - J)^T}.$$

For the selection of the estimators of the parameters k and d can be got by using the following iterative approach.

Step 1: Compute $\hat{d} = \min\left(\frac{\sigma^2}{\alpha_j^2}\right)$

Step 2: Compute a random vector J .

Step 3: Compute \hat{k}_{opt} using J and \hat{d} .

Step 4: Compute \hat{d}_{opt} .

2.2.7 Modified Two Parameter Estimator

Dorugade (2014) [8] suggested a modified two-parameter estimator, defined as:

$$\hat{\beta}_{MTP} = A_{MTP}\hat{\beta}_{OLS} \# (2.17)$$

where $A_{MTP} = [I + k(1-d)(X^T X + kdI)^{-1}][I - kd(X^T X + kdI)^{-1}]$.

The expected value and covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{MTP}$ are:

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{MTP}) = A_{MTP}\beta,$$

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{MTP}) = \sigma_{MTP}^2 A_{MTP}(X^T X)^{-1} A_{MTP}^T,$$

and σ_{MTP}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{MTP}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{MTP})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{MTP})}{n - p - 1} \# (2.18)$$

For unknow values of k and d , some well know methods are, $k_1 = \frac{p\hat{\sigma}^2}{\sum_{j=1}^p \hat{\alpha}_j^2}$ and $k_2 = median\left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{\hat{\alpha}_j^2}\right)$.

And the optimal d can be considered as:

$$\hat{d}_{opt} = \sum_{j=1}^p \frac{(\lambda_j + k)(\hat{\sigma}^2 + \lambda_j \hat{\alpha}_j^2) - \lambda_j}{k\hat{\alpha}_j^2}.$$

2.2.8 Modified Almost Unbiased Liu Estimator

Arumairajan and Wijekoon (2017) [3] proposed a modified version of the almost unbiased Liu estimator, formulated as:

$$\hat{\beta}_{MAULE} = A_{MAULE} \hat{\beta}_{OLS}, \#(2.19)$$

where $A_{MAULE} = \left(1 - (1-d)^2 (X^T X + I)^{-2}\right) (X^T X + kI)^{-1} X^T X$.

The expected value and covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{MAULE}$ are:

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{MAULE}) = A_{MAULE} \beta,$$

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{MAULE}) = \sigma_{MAULE}^2 A_{MAULE} (X^T X)^{-1} A_{MAULE}^T,$$

and σ_{MAULE}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{MAULE}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{MAULE})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{MAULE})}{n - p - 1}. \#(2.20)$$

$$\text{Now, } \hat{d}_{opt} = 1 - \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^p \frac{\lambda_j (\sigma^2 - k\alpha_j^2)}{(\lambda_{j+k})^2 (\lambda_{j+1})^2}}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^p \frac{\lambda_j (\sigma^2 + \lambda_j \alpha_j^2)}{(\lambda_{j+1})^4 (\lambda_{j+k})^2}}}$$

$$\text{And } \hat{k} = \frac{\sigma^2 (\lambda_{j+1})^2 \lambda_j - (1-d)^2 \lambda_j (\sigma^2 + \alpha_j^2)}{\alpha_j^2 (\lambda_{j+1})^2}.$$

We can obtain arithmetic mean value of k .

2.2.9 Modified Almost Unbiased Two Parameter Estimator

Proposed by Lukman, Adewuyi, Oladejo, and Olukayode (2019) [23] and defined as:

$$\hat{\beta}_{MAUTP} = A_{MAUTP} \hat{\beta}_{OLS}, \#(2.21)$$

where $A_{MAUTP} = \left(I - k^2 (1-d)^2 (X^T X + kI)^{-2}\right) (X^T X + kI)^{-1} X^T X$.

The expected value and covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{MAUTP}$ are:

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{MAUTP}) = A_{MAUTP} \beta,$$

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{MAUTP}) = \sigma_{MAUTP}^2 A_{MAUTP} (X^T X)^{-1} A_{MAUTP}^T,$$

and σ_{MAUTP}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{MAUTP}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{MAUTP})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{MAUTP})}{n - p - 1}. \#(2.22)$$

For the estimation of k and d , following Hoerl and Kennard (1970) [15], $\hat{k} = \frac{\sigma^2}{\alpha_j^2}$ and the harmonic

version of the proposed \hat{k} is $\hat{k}_{HMP} = \frac{p\sigma^2}{\sum_{j=1}^p \alpha_j^2}$,

$$\text{and } \hat{d} = \min \left(\frac{\alpha_j^2}{\frac{\sigma^2}{\alpha_j^2} + \alpha_j^2} \right).$$

2.2.10 Modified New Two Parameter Estimator

Lukman et al. (2019) [24] proposed a modified new two-parameter estimator:

$$\hat{\beta}_{MNTP} = (X^T X + kI)^{-1} [(X^T X + kdI) \hat{\beta}_{OLS} + k(1-d)b], \#(2.23)$$

where b is the prior information on β and it tends to b as k tends to infinity.

Recall that $k(1-d) = (X^T X + kI) - (X^T X + kdI)$ and let $A_{MNTP} = (X^T X + kI)^{-1} (X^T X + kdI)$. The expected value and covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{MNTP}$ are:

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{MNTP}) = A_{MNTP}\beta + (I - A_{MNTP})b,$$

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{MNTP}) = \sigma_{MNTP}^2 A_{MNTP} (X^T X)^{-1} A_{MNTP}^T,$$

and σ_{MNTP}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{MNTP}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{MNTP})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{MNTP})}{n - p - 1}. \#(2.24)$$

For k , we fixed d , from Lukman et al. (2019) [24], we get the optimal k as

$$\hat{k}_j = \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2 \lambda_j}{\lambda_j (\hat{\alpha}_j - b)^2 - \hat{d} (\lambda_j (\hat{\alpha}_j - b)^2 + \hat{\sigma}^2)}.$$

And harmonic mean version is defined as:

$$\hat{k}_{HMP} = \frac{p}{\sum_{j=1}^p 1/\hat{k}_j}.$$

Then, we get,

$$\hat{d}_{opt} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^p \left[\left(\hat{k}_j \lambda_j (\hat{\alpha}_j - b)^2 \right) - \hat{\sigma}^2 \lambda_j \right]}{\sum_{j=1}^p \left(\hat{\sigma}^2 \hat{k}_j + \lambda_j (\hat{\alpha}_j - b)^2 \right)}.$$

The selection of the estimators of the parameters k and d in $\hat{\beta}_{MNTP}$ is obtained iteratively as follows:

Step 1: Obtain an initial estimate of d using $\hat{d} = \min \left(\frac{\lambda_j (\hat{\alpha}_j - b)^2}{\lambda_j (\hat{\alpha}_j - b)^2 + \hat{\sigma}^2} \right)$

Step 2: Obtain \hat{k} using \hat{d} in step 1.

Step 3: Estimate \hat{d}_{opt} using \hat{k} in step 2.

Step 4. If \hat{d}_{opt} is negative use $\hat{d}_{opt} = \hat{d}$. However, \hat{d} takes value between 0 and 1.

2.2.11 Modified Ridge Type Estimator

Modified Ridge Type estimator (MRT) is proposed by Lukman et al. (2019) [25] which also a two-parameter estimator which is defined as:

$$\hat{\beta}_{MRT} = M_{k,d} \hat{\beta}_{OLS}, \#(2.25)$$

where $M_{k,d} = (X^T X + k(1+d)I)^{-1} (X^T X)$, k and d are biasing parameters.

The expected value and covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{MRT}$ are:

$$E(\beta_{MRT}) = M_{k,d}\beta,$$

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{MRT}) = \sigma_{MRT}^2 M_{k,d} (X^T X)^{-1} M_{k,d}^T,$$

and σ_{MRT}^2 is estimated as:

$$\widehat{\sigma}_{MRT}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\widehat{\beta}_{MRT})^T (Y - X\widehat{\beta}_{MRT})}{n - p - 1}. \# (2.26)$$

Since both shrinkage parameters k and d are unknown, they must be estimated directly from the data. The following section outlines the formulas used to obtain these parameters for different regression estimators.

Lukman et al. (2019) [25] proposed an estimator as follows:

$$\widehat{k}_j = \frac{\widehat{\sigma}^2}{(1+d)\widehat{\alpha}_j^2}.$$

Harmonic mean version of the proposed \widehat{k}_j is,

$$\widehat{k}_{HMP} = \frac{p\widehat{\sigma}^2}{\sum_{j=1}^p (1+d)\widehat{\alpha}_j^2}$$

and

$$\widehat{d}_j = \frac{\widehat{\sigma}^2}{k\widehat{\alpha}_j^2} - 1.$$

The harmonic mean version of \widehat{d}_j proposed by Lukman et al. (2019) [25] is defined as:

$$\widehat{d}_{MRT} = \frac{p}{\sum_{j=1}^p \left(\frac{1}{\widehat{d}_j}\right)}.$$

The selection of the estimators of the parameters k and d in $\widehat{\beta}_{MRT}$ is obtained iteratively as follows:

Step 1: Obtain an initial estimate of d using $\widehat{d} = \min\left(\frac{\widehat{\sigma}^2}{\widehat{\alpha}_j^2}\right)$

Step 2: Obtain \widehat{k}_{HMP} using \widehat{d} in step 1.

Step 3: Estimate \widehat{d}_{MRT} using \widehat{k}_{HMP} in step 2.

Step 4. If \widehat{d}_{opt} is negative use $\widehat{d}_{MRT} = \widehat{d}$.

2.2.12 A New Biased Estimator

A new biased two parameter estimator has been proposed by Dawood and Kibria (2020) [6] is defined as:

$$\widehat{\beta}_{DK} = A_{DK}\widehat{\beta}_{OLS} \# (2.27)$$

where $A_{DK} = (X^T X + k(1+d)I)^{-1} (X^T X - k(1+d)I)$.

The expected value and covariance matrix of $\widehat{\beta}_{DK}$ are:

$$E(\widehat{\beta}_{DK}) = A_{DK}\beta,$$

$$Var(\widehat{\beta}_{DK}) = \sigma_{DK}^2 A_{DK} (X^T X)^{-1} A_{DK}^T,$$

and σ_{DK}^2 is estimated as:

$$\widehat{\sigma}_{DK}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\widehat{\beta}_{DK})^T (Y - X\widehat{\beta}_{DK})}{n - p - 1}. \# (2.28)$$

For k , we fixed d , we get the optimal k as

$$\hat{k}_j = \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{(1+\hat{d})\left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{\lambda_j} + 2\hat{\alpha}_j^2\right)}.$$

And $k_{min} = \min(\hat{k}_j)$

Then, we get,

$$\hat{d}_{opt} = \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2 \lambda_j}{m} - 1,$$

where $m = \hat{k}(\hat{\sigma}^2 + 2\lambda_j \hat{\alpha}_j^2)$.

The selection of the estimators of the parameters k and d in $\hat{\beta}_{DK}$ is obtained iteratively as follows:

Step 1: Obtain an initial estimate of d using $\hat{d} = \min\left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{\hat{\alpha}_j^2}\right)$

Step 2: Obtain \hat{k} using \hat{d} in step 1.

Step 3: Estimate \hat{d}_{min} using \hat{k} in step 2.

Step 4. If \hat{d}_{opt} is not between 0 and 1, use $\hat{d}_{min} = \hat{d}$.

2.2.13 Generalized Two Parameter

Zeinal (2020) [36] proposed a generalized version, defined as:

$$\hat{\beta}_{GTP} = (X^T X + kI)^{-1} (X^T X + kD) \hat{\beta}_{OLS}, \# (2.29)$$

where $D = \text{diag}(d_1, d_2, \dots, d_p)$.

The expected value and covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{GTP}$ are:

$$E(\beta_{GTP}) = A_{GTP} \beta,$$

$$\text{Var}(\hat{\beta}_{GTP}) = \sigma_{MRT}^2 A_{GTP} (X^T X)^{-1} A_{GTP}^T,$$

and σ_{GTP}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{GTP}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{GTP})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{GTP})}{n - p - 1} \# (2.30)$$

where $A_{GTP} = (X^T X + kI)^{-1} (X^T X + kD)$.

For the unknown parameter, we get the optimal $d_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, p$ for fixed k

$$\hat{d}_{jopt} = \frac{(k\hat{\alpha}_j^2 - \hat{\sigma}^2)\lambda_j}{k(\hat{\sigma}^2 + \hat{\alpha}_j^2 \lambda_j)}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, p$$

Then, we get,

$$\hat{k}_j = \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{\hat{\alpha}_j^2 - d_j \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{\lambda_j} + \hat{\alpha}_j^2 \right)},$$

And take the arithmetic mean of the above mentioned k_j .

The selection of the estimators of the parameters k and d in $\hat{\beta}_{GTP}$ is obtained iteratively as follows:

Step 1: Obtain an initial estimate of $\hat{d}_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, p$ using $\hat{d} = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{\hat{\alpha}_j^2}\right)$

- Step 2: Obtain \hat{k} using \hat{d} in step 1.
 Step 3: Estimate \hat{d}_{jopt} using \hat{k} in step 2.
 Step 4. If \hat{d}_{jopt} is negative use $\hat{d}_{jopt} = \hat{d}_j$

2.2.14 Defining Two-Parameter Estimator

Developed by Şiray et al. (2021) [32] and defined as:

$$\hat{\beta}_{DTP} = A_{DTP} \hat{\beta}_{OLS}, \# (2.31)$$

where $A_{DTP} = (X^T X + kI)^{-1} \left(X^T X + \frac{k}{d} (X^T X + I)^{-1} (X^T X + dI) \right)$.

The expected value and covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{DTP}$ are:

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{DTP}) = A_{DTP} \beta,$$

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{DTP}) = \sigma_{DTP}^2 A_{DTP} (X^T X)^{-1} A_{DTP}^T,$$

and σ_{MNTP}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{DTP}^2 = \frac{(Y - X \hat{\beta}_{DTP})^T (Y - X \hat{\beta}_{DTP})}{n - p - 1}. \# (2.32)$$

Now, $\hat{k}_j = \frac{\sigma^2 d \lambda_j (\lambda_j + 1)}{(d-1) \lambda_j^2 \alpha_j^2 - \sigma^2 (\lambda_j + d)}$, we can take the harmonic mean and median of \hat{k}_j .

And $\hat{d}_j = \frac{\sigma^2 k \lambda_j + k \lambda_j^2 \alpha_j^2}{k \lambda_j^2 \alpha_j^2 - \sigma^2 \lambda_j^2 - \sigma^2 \lambda_j - \sigma^2 k}$, we also can take the harmonic mean and median of \hat{d}_j .

The estimation methods for the biasing parameters are given so far.

Step 1: Obtain an initial estimate of \hat{d} using $\hat{d} = \max \left[\frac{\lambda_j (\sigma^2 + \lambda_j \alpha_j^2)}{\lambda_j^2 \alpha_j^2 - \sigma^2} \right]$

Step 2: Obtain \hat{k}_j using \hat{d} in step 1.

Step 3: Estimate \hat{d}_j using \hat{k}_j in step 2.

Step 4. If \hat{d}_j is negative use $\hat{d}_j = \hat{d}$.

2.2.15 Unbiased Modified Two-Parameter Estimator

Introduced by Abidoye, Ajayi, Adewale, and Ogunjobi (2022) [1] is defined as

$$\hat{\beta}_{UMTP} = R_{k,d} \hat{\beta}_{OLS} + (1 - R_{k,d}) J, \# (2.33)$$

where $R_{k,d} = (X^T X + kdI)^{-1} X^T X$ and $J \sim N(\beta, \sigma^2 (kdI)^{-1})$ for $k > 0, 0 < d < 1$ with J being uncorrelated with $\hat{\beta}_{ols}$ and the prior information J is a random vector for specified mean and covariance.

The expected value and covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{UMTP}$ are:

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{UMTP}) = \beta,$$

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{UMTP}) = \sigma_{UMTP}^2 (X^T X + kdI)^{-1},$$

and σ_{UMTP}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{UMTP}^2 = \frac{(Y - X \hat{\beta}_{UMTP})^T (Y - X \hat{\beta}_{UMTP})}{n - p - 1}. \# (2.34)$$

To examine the performance of this parameter over other existing estimators, the bias parameters k and d are chosen. In this study, they choose $k = \frac{p\hat{\sigma}^2}{\sum_{j=1}^p \hat{\alpha}_j^2}$ and $d = \sum_{j=1}^p \left[\frac{(\lambda_j+k)(\hat{\sigma}^2+\lambda_j\hat{\alpha}_j^2)-\lambda_j}{k\hat{\alpha}_j^2} \right]$.

2.2.16 Modified New Two Parameter Estimator

Proposed by Ahmad and Aslam (2022) [2] is defined as

$$\hat{\beta}_{MNTPE} = C_0 \hat{\beta}_{OLS}, \# (2.35)$$

where $C_0 = (X^T X + I)^{-1} (X^T X + dI) (X^T X + kdI)^{-1} X^T X$.

The expected value and covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{MNTPE}$ are:

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{MNTPE}) = C_0 \beta,$$

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{MNTPE}) = \sigma_{MNTPE}^2 C_0 (X^T X)^{-1} C_0^T,$$

and σ_{MNTPE}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{MNTPE}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{MNTPE})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{MNTPE})}{n - p - 1}. \# (2.36)$$

$$\text{Now, } k_{opt} = \frac{\sigma^2(\lambda_j+d)-(1-d)\lambda_j\alpha_j^2}{d(\lambda_j+1)\alpha_j^2}.$$

We take the harmonic mean of \hat{k} values, and

$$d_{opt} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^p \lambda_j(\alpha_j^2 - \sigma^2)}{\sum_{j=1}^p (\lambda_j\alpha_j^2 + \sigma^2 - k\lambda_j\alpha_j^2)}.$$

The selection of the estimators of the parameters k and d in $\hat{\beta}_{MNTPE}$ is obtained iteratively as follows:

Step 1: Obtain an initial estimate of \hat{d}_{max} using $\hat{d} = \max \left[\frac{(\alpha_j^2 - \sigma^2)\lambda_j}{(\sigma^2 + \lambda_j\alpha_j^2)} \right]$

Step 2: Obtain \hat{k}_{opt} using \hat{d} in step 1.

Step 3: Estimate \hat{d}_{opt} using \hat{k}_{opt} in step 2.

Step 4. If \hat{d}_{opt} is negative use $\hat{d}_{opt} = \hat{d}_{max}$

2.2.17 Modified Liu Ridge Type Estimator

Proposed by Aslam and Ahmad (2022) [4] is defined as

$$\hat{\beta}_{MLRT} = A_{MLRT} \hat{\beta}_{OLS}, \# (2.37)$$

where $A_{MLRT} = (X^T X + I)^{-1} (X^T X + d) (X^T X + k(1+d)I)^{-1} X^T X$.

The expected value and covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{MLRT}$ are:

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{MLRT}) = A_{MLRT} \beta,$$

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{MLRT}) = \sigma_{MLRT}^2 A_{MLRT} (X^T X)^{-1} A_{MLRT}^T,$$

and σ_{MLRT}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{MLRT}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{MLRT})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{MLRT})}{n - p - 1}. \# (2.38)$$

$$\text{Now, } k_{opt} = \frac{\sigma^2(\lambda_j+d)-\lambda_j(1-d)\alpha_j^2}{(1+d)(\lambda_j+1)\alpha_j^2} \text{ and we can take the max values of } \hat{k}.$$

$$\text{And } d_{opt} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^p \frac{(\lambda_j + k(\lambda_{j+1})) [\lambda_j^2 - k\lambda_j^2 - k\lambda_j] \alpha_j^2 - \sigma^2 \lambda_j [\lambda_j^2 - k\lambda_j^2 - k\lambda_j]}{(\lambda_{j+1})^2}}{\sum_{j=1}^p \frac{\sigma^2 [\lambda_j^2 - k\lambda_j^2 - k\lambda_j] + (\lambda_j - k(\lambda_{j+1})) [\lambda_j^2 - k\lambda_j^2 - k\lambda_j] \alpha_j^2}{(\lambda_{j+1})^2}}$$

The selection of the estimators of the parameters k and d is obtained iteratively as follows:

Step 1: Obtain an initial estimate of $\hat{d}_{max,j} = 1, 2, \dots, p$ using $\hat{d} = \max \left[\frac{(\alpha_j^2 - \sigma^2) \lambda_j}{(\sigma^2 + \lambda_j \alpha_j^2)} \right]$

Step 2: Obtain \hat{k}_{opt} using \hat{d} in step 1.

Step 3: Estimate \hat{d}_{opt} using \hat{k}_{opt} in step 2.

Step 4. If \hat{d}_{opt} is negative use $\hat{d}_{opt} = \hat{d}_{max}$

2.2.18 New Biased Regression Two Parameter Estimator

Proposed by Dawoud, Lukman and Haadi (2022) [7] is defined as

$$\hat{\beta}_{NBR} = RWM\hat{\beta}_{OLS}, \#(2.39)$$

where, $R = (X^T X + kI)^{-1} (X^T X + kdI)$ and WM for KL and $W = (X^T X + kI)^{-1}$ and $M = (X^T X - kI)$.

The expected value and covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{NBR}$ are:

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{NBR}) = RWM\beta,$$

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{NBR}) = \sigma_{NBR}^2 RWM (X^T X)^{-1} M^T W^T R^T,$$

and σ_{NBR}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{NBR}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{NBR})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{NBR})}{n - p - 1}. \#(2.40)$$

Here, $\hat{k} = \frac{-(\lambda_j^2 \alpha_j^2 (3-d) + \sigma^2 \lambda_j (1-d))}{2(\sigma^2 d + \lambda_j \alpha_j^2 (1+d))} + \frac{\lambda_j \sqrt{\lambda_j (\alpha_j^2)^2 (d-3)^2 + 2\lambda_j \sigma^2 \alpha_j^2 (5-2d+d^2) + (\sigma^2)^2 (1+d)^2}}{2(\sigma^2 d + \lambda_j \alpha_j^2 (1+d))}$ we take the minimum values.

And $\hat{d} = \frac{\lambda_j^2 (\sigma^2 - 3\alpha_j^2 k) - \lambda_j k (\sigma^2 + \alpha_j^2 k)}{k(k - \lambda_j) (\sigma^2 + \lambda_j \alpha_j^2)}$ and taking the minimum values of this.

The selection of the estimators of the parameters k and d is obtained iteratively as follows:

Step 1: Obtain an initial estimate of \hat{d} using $\hat{d} = \min \left[\frac{\sigma^2}{\alpha_j^2} \right]$

Step 2: Obtain \hat{k}_{opt} using \hat{d} in step 1.

Step 3: Estimate \hat{d}_{opt} using \hat{k}_{opt} in step 2.

Step 4. If \hat{d}_{opt} is negative use $\hat{d}_{opt} = \hat{d}$

2.2.19 Biased Two Parameter

Proposed by Idowu, Oladapo, Owolabi and Ayinde (2022) [17] is defined as:

$$\hat{\beta}_{BTP} = EH\hat{\beta}_{OLS}, \#(2.41)$$

where, $E = (X^T X + I)^{-1} (X^T X - dI)$ and $H = (X^T X + k(1+d)I)^{-1} (X^T X - k(1+d)I)$.

The expected value and covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{NRT}$ are:

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{BTP}) = EH\beta,$$

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{BTP}) = \sigma_{BTP}^2 EH(X^T X)^{-1} H^T E^T,$$

and σ_{BTP}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{BTP}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{BTP})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{BTP})}{n - p - 1} \# (2.42)$$

$$\text{Now, } \hat{k} = \frac{\sigma^2 \lambda_j (d - \lambda_j) + \alpha_j^2 \lambda_j^2 (d + 1)}{\sigma^2 (1 + d) (d - \lambda_j) - \alpha_j^2 \lambda_j (1 + d) (2\lambda_j - d + 1)}.$$

And,

$$\hat{d} = \frac{-(\sigma^2 \lambda_j - \sigma^2 k + \alpha_j^2 \lambda_j^2 + \sigma^2 \lambda_j k + 2\alpha_j^2 \lambda_j^2 k)}{2(\sigma^2 k + \alpha_j^2 \lambda_j k)} +$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{(\alpha_j^2)^2 \lambda_j^2 k (2\lambda_j k + k + \lambda_j) + \sigma^2 \alpha_j^2 \lambda_j^2 k (k - \lambda_j) + \sigma^2 \alpha_j^2 (2\sigma^2 \lambda_j k + k + \lambda_j) + (\sigma^2)^2 \lambda_j k (k - \lambda_j)}}{(\sigma^2 k + \alpha_j^2 \lambda_j k)}.$$

2.2.20 New Two Parameter Estimator

A new two parameter estimator has been proposed by Owolabi, Ayinde, Idowu, Oladapo and Lukman (2022 [26]) is defined as:

$$\hat{\beta}_{NTP} = A_{NTP} \hat{\beta}_{OLS} \# (2.43)$$

where $A_{NTP} = (X^T X + kdI)^{-1} (X^T X - kdI)$.

The expected value and covariance matrix of $\hat{\beta}_{NTP}$ are:

$$E(\hat{\beta}_{NTP}) = A_{NTP} \beta,$$

$$Var(\hat{\beta}_{NTP}) = \sigma_{NTP}^2 A_{NTP} (X^T X)^{-1} A_{NTP}^T,$$

and σ_{NTP}^2 is estimated as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{NTP}^2 = \frac{(Y - X\hat{\beta}_{NTP})^T (Y - X\hat{\beta}_{NTP})}{n - p - 1} \# (2.44)$$

Now, $\hat{k} = \frac{\sigma^2}{d(2\alpha_j^2 + \frac{\sigma^2}{\lambda_j})}$ and the harmonic mean version is defined as $\hat{k}_{HM} = \frac{\sigma^2}{\Sigma d(2\alpha_j^2 + \frac{\sigma^2}{\lambda_j})}$,

and $\hat{d}_p = \frac{\sigma^2}{k(2\alpha_j^2 + \frac{\sigma^2}{\lambda_j})}$.

The selection of the estimators of the parameters k and d is obtained iteratively as follows:

Step 1: Obtain an initial estimate of \hat{d} using $\hat{d} = \min \left[\frac{\sigma^2}{\alpha_j^2} \right]$

Step 2: Obtain \hat{k}_{opt} using \hat{d} in step 1.

Step 3: Estimate \hat{d}_{opt} using \hat{k}_{opt} in step 2.

Step 4. If \hat{d}_{opt} is negative use $\hat{d}_{opt} = \hat{d}$

To test the j th component of the parameter vector β equal to zero, the approach of Halawa and Bassiouni (2000) [11] is used with the following t-test statistic:

$$t^* = \frac{\hat{\beta}_j^*}{SE(\hat{\beta}_j^*)} \# (2.45)$$

where $\hat{\beta}_j^* = \hat{\beta}_{j(LTE)}, \hat{\beta}_{j(TP)}, \hat{\beta}_{j(NBE)}, \hat{\beta}_{j(YC)}, \dots$ is the j th element of $\hat{\beta}_{LTE}, \hat{\beta}_{TP}, \hat{\beta}_{NBE}, \hat{\beta}_{YC}, \dots$ respectively and $SE(\hat{\beta}_j^*)$ is the square root of the i th element of $Var(\hat{\beta}_j^*)$. They are defined under equation (2.6), (2.8), (2.10), ... respectively. Under the null hypothesis, the test statistics (2.45) has been shown to be approximately distributed as a student t-distribution with $n - p - 1$ degrees of freedom.

3. Simulation Study

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the test statistics through a Monte Carlo simulation. Our analysis proceeds in two stages: first, we examine the empirical type I error of the tests in section 3.1, and then we study the empirical power of the tests in section 3.2.

3.1 Type I Error Rated Simulation Procedure

3.1.1 Simulation Technique

In the simulation design, the explanatory variables X are generated using the expression $H\Lambda^{0.5}G^T$, where H is an $n \times p$ matrix with orthogonal columns, Λ is a diagonal matrix containing the eigenvalues of the correlation matrix, and G represent the normalized eigenvectors of the correlation matrix, respectively. This method allows the predictor variables to be systematically created, making it possible to examination of type I error within the context of regression analysis.

For this study, we generate n observations for the explanatory variables according to the regression model:

$$Y_i = \beta_1 X_{i1} + \beta_2 X_{i2} + \dots + \beta_p X_{ip} + \epsilon_i, \# (3.1)$$

where, the error terms ϵ_i are independent distributed as normal $(0, \sigma^2)$. The performance of the test is assessed based on their Type I error rates under various choices of shrinkage parameters. We consider different values of sample sizes $n = 30, 50, \text{ and } 100$, and different explanatory variables $p = 3, 5, \text{ and } 10$. Also, various correlations $\rho = 0.90, \text{ and } 0.99$ are chosen, and the standard deviations of errors $\sigma = 1$. Each scenario was replicated 5000 times using R software.

Following Halawa and Bassiouni (2000) [11], the most and least favorable orientations of β are derived from normalized eigenvectors corresponding to the largest and smallest eigenvalues of $X^T X$ in correlation form. The most favorable (MF) orientation is given by $\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{p}}\right) 1_p$, where 1_p is a vector of ones, while the least favorable (LF) orientation corresponds to any normalized vector orthogonal to 1_p . In the MF orientation, all coefficients of β are equal, whereas in the LF case, each component are equally likely.

Previous findings indicate that LF orientations typically yield tests that maintain the nominal Type I error level across estimators, while MF orientations may lead to higher Type I error rates than expected. For this reason, the MF orientation is useful to identify and discard tests that are too liberal in rejecting the null hypothesis Accordingly, our simulation focuses on the MF orientation of β .

To evaluate type I error, the j th component of the orientation vector is set to zero, denoted as $\beta = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{p}}\right) \mathbf{1}_p$, with $\beta_j = 0$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, p$. The test statistics are then computed from the models, and type I error rates are estimated as the proportion of test statistics exceeding the critical values from the t -distribution with $n - p - 1$ degrees of freedom. This approach allows us to assess how accurately the tests maintain the nominal rejection rate when the null hypothesis is true, thereby providing empirical size estimates.

Table 1: Type I error for $\rho = 0.90$, and $\alpha = 0.05$, MF orientation

p		3			5			10		
n	30	50	100	30	50	100	30	50	100	avg
OLS	0.0485	0.0455	0.0454	0.0466	0.0471	0.0506	0.0449	0.047	0.0484	0.0471
LTE	0.0679	0.0691	0.0701	0.049	0.0519	0.0574	0.0364	0.0425	0.0474	0.0546
TP1	0.0487	0.0468	0.0457	0.0465	0.047	0.0506	0.0449	0.047	0.0484	0.0473
TP2	0.0493	0.0475	0.0463	0.0457	0.0472	0.0507	0.0427	0.0458	0.0481	0.047
NBE1	0.0586	0.0571	0.0579	0.0464	0.0495	0.0546	0.0363	0.0425	0.0469	0.05
NBE2	0.0575	0.0561	0.0559	0.0468	0.0496	0.0542	0.0364	0.0425	0.0473	0.0496
YC1	0.0618	0.0674	0.0732	0.0955	0.1181	0.1303	0.211	0.2789	0.3133	0.1499
YC2	0.0468	0.0586	0.0676	0.0594	0.0721	0.0893	0.0633	0.0883	0.1059	0.0724
YC3	0.0523	0.0519	0.0538	0.0481	0.0522	0.0578	0.0374	0.0444	0.0497	0.0497
AUTP1	0.0394	0.0385	0.0399	0.0342	0.0373	0.0428	0.0269	0.032	0.0372	0.0365
AUTP2	0.0451	0.0443	0.0449	0.0469	0.0493	0.0506	0.0468	0.0541	0.0538	0.0484
UTP	0.0475	0.1139	0.336	0.0092	0.0212	0.0624	0.0015	0.0033	0.0075	0.0669
MTP1	0.1167	0.1506	0.1772	0.2387	0.315	0.3619	0.4244	0.6272	0.7175	0.3477
MTP2	0.1157	0.1495	0.177	0.2371	0.3136	0.3606	0.4229	0.6263	0.7167	0.3466
MAULE	0.0002	0.0009	0.0011	0.0001	0.0001	0.0002	0.0001	0.0001	0.0002	0.0003
MAUTP	0.0777	0.0815	0.0853	0.0676	0.0776	0.086	0.0366	0.0469	0.0535	0.0681
MNTP	0.1403	0.1476	0.1435	0.0717	0.0753	0.0785	0.0531	0.0566	0.0596	0.0918
DK	0.0589	0.0592	0.0587	0.0463	0.048	0.052	0.043	0.0457	0.0482	0.0511
MRT	0.0545	0.0547	0.0561	0.0459	0.0497	0.0542	0.0353	0.042	0.0474	0.0489
GTP	0.0281	0.0327	0.0351	0.0171	0.0192	0.0252	0.0126	0.0161	0.0193	0.0228
DTP1	0.165	0.1809	0.2054	0.2961	0.3404	0.37	0.4924	0.6027	0.6595	0.368
DTP2	0.1739	0.1941	0.2113	0.299	0.3398	0.3669	0.5564	0.6721	0.7318	0.3939
UMPT	0.9901	0.9935	0.9968	0.9964	0.9982	0.9993	0.9986	0.9996	0.9998	0.9969
MNTPE	0.1568	0.1731	0.1917	0.2694	0.3031	0.3247	0.3376	0.4188	0.469	0.2938
MLRT	0.1401	0.1629	0.1761	0.2668	0.3071	0.3322	0.4937	0.6215	0.6904	0.3545
NBR	0.0199	0.0439	0.0898	0.0057	0.0111	0.0188	0.0017	0.0019	0.0013	0.0216
BTP	0.0703	0.0781	0.0865	0.1655	0.207	0.2324	0.4234	0.5115	0.5522	0.2585
NTP	0.0485	0.0464	0.0451	0.0461	0.0472	0.0508	0.0447	0.0469	0.0484	0.0471

Table 2: Type I error for $\rho = 0.99$, and $\alpha = 0.05$, MF orientation

P		3			5			10			
n	30	50	100	30	50	100	30	50	100	avg	
OLS	0.0443	0.0485	0.0467	0.0455	0.045	0.0474	0.0451	0.047	0.0482	0.0464	
LTE	0.0482	0.0544	0.0533	0.0416	0.0439	0.0471	0.0352	0.0417	0.0456	0.0457	
TP1	0.0442	0.0483	0.0469	0.0454	0.045	0.0473	0.0451	0.047	0.0482	0.0464	
TP2	0.0457	0.0507	0.0495	0.0445	0.0448	0.0472	0.0426	0.0456	0.0476	0.0465	
NBE1	0.0462	0.0521	0.0512	0.0416	0.0436	0.0469	0.0352	0.0417	0.0455	0.0449	
NBE2	0.0477	0.0537	0.0533	0.0416	0.0438	0.047	0.0352	0.0416	0.0456	0.0455	
YC1	0.1587	0.1844	0.2015	0.2666	0.2887	0.3094	0.3701	0.4869	0.5574	0.3137	
YC2	0.075	0.092	0.1002	0.075	0.0937	0.108	0.0596	0.0853	0.1035	0.088	
YC3	0.0444	0.0504	0.0483	0.0415	0.0436	0.0478	0.035	0.0415	0.0456	0.0442	
AUTP1	0.0339	0.0377	0.0383	0.0323	0.0355	0.0399	0.0254	0.0317	0.0361	0.0345	
AUTP2	0.0429	0.0476	0.0467	0.0435	0.0445	0.0468	0.0406	0.0459	0.049	0.0453	
UTP	0.0104	0.015	0.0315	0.0039	0.0062	0.0137	0.0009	0.0018	0.003	0.0096	
MTP1	0.131	0.1655	0.1894	0.2591	0.3366	0.3912	0.4684	0.6709	0.755	0.3741	
MTP2	0.1307	0.1651	0.1891	0.2588	0.3365	0.391	0.4683	0.6709	0.755	0.3739	
MAULE	0.0001	0.0001	0.0002	0.0001	0.0001	0.0002	0.0001	0.0001	0.0002	0.0002	
MAUTP	0.0524	0.0596	0.0612	0.0439	0.048	0.0523	0.0321	0.0395	0.0452	0.0482	
MNTP	0.0843	0.0914	0.0902	0.0493	0.049	0.0508	0.0459	0.0476	0.0491	0.062	
DK	0.0466	0.0522	0.051	0.0444	0.0446	0.047	0.0429	0.0458	0.0477	0.0469	
MRT	0.0473	0.0526	0.0538	0.0407	0.0434	0.0467	0.0336	0.0407	0.0454	0.0449	
GTP	0.0102	0.0108	0.0113	0.0073	0.0097	0.0104	0.0046	0.0087	0.0124	0.0095	
DTP1	0.1673	0.1903	0.2055	0.3222	0.3716	0.4059	0.5874	0.7021	0.7554	0.412	
DTP2	0.1661	0.1889	0.2045	0.3278	0.3714	0.4074	0.5982	0.7142	0.7701	0.4165	
UMPT	0.9853	0.9893	0.9941	0.9957	0.9975	0.9987	0.9992	0.9997	0.9998	0.9955	
MNTPE	0.1659	0.1873	0.2009	0.3278	0.371	0.4054	0.5914	0.707	0.7626	0.4133	
MLRT	0.1672	0.1869	0.2005	0.3252	0.3653	0.4028	0.5719	0.7044	0.766	0.41	
NBR	0.0059	0.008	0.015	0.0026	0.0028	0.0021	0.001	0.0005	0.0003	0.0042	
BTP	0.0459	0.0516	0.0567	0.1339	0.1839	0.2149	0.3678	0.4688	0.5179	0.2268	
NTP	0.0441	0.0481	0.047	0.0451	0.045	0.0474	0.0448	0.0468	0.0482	0.0463	

3.1.2 Simulation Results

Tables 1 and 2 represent the empirical sizes of the tests under the MF orientation for correlation levels of 0.90, and 0.99. Assuming a nominal type I error rate of 5% and 5,000 simulation

replications, the expected range for the observed error rate is $0.05 \pm 2 \sqrt{\frac{0.05 \times 0.95}{5000}} \approx (4.4\%, 5.6\%)$. Any test whose average empirical type I error exceeded 6% was excluded from further comparison to maintain reliability.

Inspection of Tables 1 and 2 reveals that several estimators show type I error rates greater than the 6% threshold under the MF orientation, making them unsuitable for recommendation.

3.2 Statistical Power Simulation Procedure

3.2.1 Simulation Technique for Statistical Power

In this section of the study, we compare various test statistics in terms of their statistical power. Following the methodology of Gokpinar and Ebegil (2016) [10], our goal is to measure how effectively each test identifies false null hypotheses by computing empirical power. Evaluating the rejection rates under alternatives provides insights into the relative performance and robustness of the tests, offering guidance to researchers in selecting the most appropriate procedure for regression models.

Since the earlier type I error analysis revealed that some tests were too liberal, those with empirical sizes well above the 5% nominal level were excluded. The remaining procedures are compared with respect to power. To generate alternatives, the j th element of the β vector is modified to $Jw(0)\sigma\beta_j$, where J is a positive integer and $w^2(0) = (1 + (p - 2)\rho)/[(1 - \rho)(1 + (p - 1)\rho)]$. The value of J is selected so that, for each combination of correlation and number of predictors, the most powerful test achieves maximum power. For this analysis, we take $J = 4$. This setup enables us to compare the relative power of the tests across different conditions.

Power is estimated from 5,000 replications by calculating the proportion of cases where the absolute value of the test statistic exceeds the critical value $t_{0.025, (n-p-1)}$. Simulations are conducted across all design choices: sample sizes $n = 30, 50, 100$, predictor counts $p = 3, 5, 10$ and correlation levels $\rho = 0.90, 0.99$. By systematically varying these parameters, we obtain a broad picture of the power properties of each method and can assess their relative effectiveness in identifying true effects.

Table 3: Power of test for $\rho = 0.90$ and $\alpha = 0.05$.

p		3			5			10			
n	30	50	100	30	50	100	30	50	100	avg	
OLS	0.5977	0.608	0.6285	0.3939	0.4035	0.422	0.2116	0.2265	0.2368	0.4143	
LTE	0.9319	0.9399	0.9423	0.648	0.6741	0.6973	0.2375	0.2786	0.3062	0.6284	
TP1	0.6325	0.6444	0.6635	0.4003	0.4108	0.4299	0.2121	0.2272	0.2375	0.4287	
TP2	0.7933	0.8143	0.8266	0.4568	0.4763	0.503	0.2211	0.2436	0.2578	0.5103	
NBE1	0.8999	0.9145	0.9174	0.5932	0.6258	0.6549	0.2289	0.2694	0.2968	0.6001	
NBE2	0.9159	0.9272	0.931	0.6266	0.6544	0.6806	0.2361	0.2771	0.3047	0.6171	
YC3	0.8529	0.8793	0.8891	0.5565	0.5972	0.6298	0.2234	0.2655	0.2932	0.5763	
AUTP1	0.49	0.5329	0.5869	0.2837	0.3072	0.3576	0.1411	0.1591	0.1728	0.3368	
AUTP2	0.6475	0.6504	0.6649	0.4646	0.4664	0.4664	0.2358	0.2715	0.2858	0.4615	

DK	0.8008	0.8161	0.8251	0.4733	0.4922	0.5176	0.2202	0.2414	0.2545	0.5157
MRT	0.8847	0.895	0.9011	0.6063	0.6367	0.6645	0.2389	0.2831	0.3124	0.6025
GTP	0.6527	0.6585	0.6731	0.4102	0.423	0.4485	0.1741	0.2091	0.2326	0.4313
NBR	0.0098	0.0107	0.0471	0.0016	0.0003	0.0006	0.0003	0.0004	0.0006	0.0078
NTP	0.6728	0.6901	0.7075	0.4149	0.4268	0.4481	0.2146	0.2307	0.241	0.4496

Table 4: Power of test for $\rho = 0.99$ and $\alpha = 0.05$.

p	3			5			10			
n	30	50	100	30	50	100	30	50	100	avg
OLS	0.5896	0.6055	0.6279	0.3901	0.405	0.4206	0.2117	0.2275	0.2345	0.4125
LTE	0.9333	0.9365	0.9438	0.6022	0.6354	0.6603	0.2167	0.2529	0.275	0.6062
TP1	0.6289	0.6468	0.6685	0.3965	0.412	0.4272	0.2122	0.2279	0.2351	0.4283
TP2	0.8171	0.8359	0.8498	0.4463	0.4696	0.4936	0.2162	0.2371	0.2478	0.5126
NBE1	0.8913	0.9076	0.9225	0.5268	0.5819	0.6178	0.2094	0.2471	0.2696	0.5749
NBE2	0.9268	0.9309	0.9393	0.5997	0.6345	0.6586	0.2172	0.2537	0.2758	0.6041
YC3	0.4129	0.7207	0.8393	0.343	0.4591	0.5424	0.1831	0.2307	0.2584	0.4433
AUTP1	0.3562	0.4221	0.5112	0.1898	0.217	0.2706	0.1073	0.1201	0.1307	0.2583
AUTP2	0.6009	0.6118	0.6335	0.4063	0.4208	0.4307	0.2068	0.2331	0.2497	0.4215
DK	0.8409	0.85	0.8627	0.459	0.4825	0.5077	0.216	0.2353	0.2452	0.5221
MRT	0.9113	0.9166	0.9273	0.6084	0.6423	0.6642	0.2185	0.2584	0.2834	0.6034
GTP	0.7617	0.7689	0.7788	0.5124	0.5363	0.5613	0.1932	0.2419	0.2727	0.5141
NBR	0.0001	0.0001	0.0004	0.0001	0.0001	0.0002	0.0001	0.0001	0.0002	0.0002
NTP	0.6689	0.6902	0.7115	0.4097	0.4263	0.4432	0.214	0.2301	0.2375	0.4479

3.2.2 Statistical Power Simulation Results

From the results presented in Tables 3 and 4, it is evident that power increases with larger sample sizes when the number of predictors is held constant, which aligns with theoretical expectations. Moreover, across both correlation levels ($\rho = 0.90, 0.99$), most of the considered tests demonstrate higher power than the standard OLS based t -test. Among the two-parameter approaches, estimators such as LTE, NBE2, and MRT consistently achieve stronger performance, while the YC3 estimator also delivers favorable results. These outcomes highlight the advantage of Ridge-type and related biased estimators in improving the power of hypothesis testing in regression models, especially when multicollinearity is present.

4 Some Concluding Remarks

This study examined a range of test statistics proposed in the literature for evaluating regression coefficients in the presence of multicollinearity within linear regression models. Two parameter biased estimators were included in the analysis. Using Monte Carlo simulations under varying conditions, we compared the tests in terms of empirical size and statistical power. The results show that several two-parameter approaches performed well, with LTE, NBE2, and MRT achieving

notably higher power than many others. These findings offer practical guidance for choosing suitable test statistics when multicollinearity is present, thereby contributing to improved regression methodology and more dependable inference for applied researchers.

References:

1. Abidoye, A. O., Ajayi, I. M., Adewale, F. L., & Ogunjobi, J. O. (2022). Unbiased Modified Two-Parameter Estimator for the Linear Regression Model. *Journal of Scientific Research*, 14(3), 785-795.
2. Ahmad, S., & Aslam, M. (2022). Another proposal about the new two-parameter estimator for linear regression model with correlated regressors. *Communications in Statistics-Simulation and Computation*, 51(6), 3054-3072.
3. Arumairajan, S., & Wijekoon, P. (2017). Modified almost unbiased Liu estimator in linear regression model. *Communications in Mathematics and Statistics*, 5, 261-276.
4. Aslam, M., & Ahmad, S. (2022). The modified Liu-ridge-type estimator: a new class of biased estimators to address multicollinearity. *Communications in Statistics-Simulation and Computation*, 51(11), 6591-6609.
5. Cule, E., Vineis, P., & De Iorio, M. (2011). Significance testing in ridge regression for genetic data. *BMC bioinformatics*, 12, 1-15.
6. Dawoud, I., and Kibria, B. M. G. A new biased estimator to combat the multicollinearity of the Gaussian linear regression model. *Stats*, 3(4) (2020), 526- 541.
7. Dawoud, I., Lukman, A. F., & Haadi, A. R. (2022). A new biased regression estimator: Theory, simulation and application. *Scientific African*, 15, e01100.
8. Dorugade, A. V. (2014). A modified two-parameter estimator in linear regression. *Statistics in Transition. New Series*, 15(1), 23-36.
9. Ehsanes Saleh, A. M., & Kibria, B. M. G. (1993). Performance of some new preliminary test ridge regression estimators and their properties. *Communications in Statistics-Theory and Methods*, 22(10), 2747-2764.
10. Gökpınar, E., and Ebeğil, M. (2016). A study on tests of hypothesis based on ridge estimator. *Gazi University Journal of Science*, 29(4), 769-781.
11. Halawa, A. M., and El Bassiouni, M. Y. (2000). Tests of regression coefficients under ridge regression models. *Journal of Statistical Computation and Simulation*, 65(1-4), 341-356.
12. Hoerl, A. E., & Kennard, R. W. (1970). Ridge regression: Biased estimation for nonorthogonal problems. *Technometrics*, 12(1), 55-67.
13. Hoerl, A. E., Kennard, R. W., and Baldwin, K. F. (1975). Ridge regression: some simulations. *Communications in Statistics-Theory and Methods*, 4(2), 105-123.
14. Hoque, M. A., Bursac, Z., & Kibria, B. M. G. (2025). Inferences About Two-Parameter Multicollinear Gaussian Linear Regression Models: An Empirical Type I Error and Power Comparison. *Stats*, 8(2), 28. <https://doi.org/10.3390/stats8020028>
15. Hoque, M. A., and Kibria, B. M. G. (2023). Some one and two parameter estimators for the multicollinear gaussian linear regression model: simulations and applications. *Surveys in Mathematics and its Applications*, 18, 183-221.
16. Hoque, M. A., & Kibria, B. M. G. (2024). Performance of some estimators for the multicollinear logistic regression model: theory, simulation, and applications. *Research in Statistics*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/27684520.2024.2364747>.
17. Idowu, J. I., Oladapo, O. J., Owolabi, A. T., & Ayinde, K. (2022). On the biased Two-Parameter Estimator to Combat Multicollinearity in Linear Regression Model. *African Scientific Reports*, 188-204.

18. Kibria, B. G. (2003). Performance of some new ridge regression estimators. *Communications in Statistics-Simulation and Computation*, 32(2), 419-435.
19. Kibria, B. M. G and Banik, S. Some Ridge Regression Estimators and Their Performances. *Journal of Modern Applied Statistical Methods*. 15 (1) (2016), 206-238.
20. Kibria, G., and Banik, S. (2019). A simulation study on the size and power Properties of some ridge regression Tests. *Applications and Applied Mathematics: An International Journal (AAM)*, 14(2), 7.
21. Kibria, B. M. G., and Lukman, A. F. A new ridge-type estimator for the linear regression model: Simulations and applications. *Scientifica*, 2020.
22. Liu, K. (2003). Using Liu-type estimator to combat collinearity. *Communications in Statistics-Theory and Methods*, 32(5), 1009-1020.
23. Lukman, A. F., Adewuyi, E., Oladejo, N., & Olukayode, A. (2019, November). Modified almost unbiased two-parameter estimator in linear regression model. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* (Vol. 640, No. 1, p. 012119). IOP Publishing.
24. Lukman, A. F., Ayinde, K., Siok Kun, S., & Adewuyi, E. T. (2019). A modified new two-parameter estimator in a linear regression model. *Modelling and Simulation in Engineering*, 2019(1), 6342702.
25. Lukman, A. F., Ayinde, K., Binuomote, S., & Clement, O. A. (2019). Modified ridge-type estimator to combat multicollinearity: Application to chemical data. *Journal of Chemometrics*, 33(5), e3125.
26. Owolabi, A. T., Ayinde, K., Idowu, J. I., Oladapo, O. J., & Lukman, A. F. (2022). A new two-parameter estimator in the linear regression model with correlated regressors. *Journal of Statistics Applications & Probability*, 11(2), 185-201.
27. Özkale, M. R., & Kaciranlar, S. (2007). The restricted and unrestricted two-parameter estimators. *Communications in Statistics—Theory and Methods*, 36(15), 2707-2725.
28. Perez-Melo, S., and Kibria, B. M. G. (2020). On some test statistics for testing the regression coefficients in presence of multicollinearity: a simulation study. *Stats*, 3(1), 40-55.
29. Perez-Melo, S., Bursac, Z., and Kibria, B. M. G. (2022). Comparison of Test Statistics for Testing the Regression Coefficients in the OLS, Ridge, Liu and Kibria-Lukman Linear Regression Model: A Simulation Study. In *JSM Proceedings, Biometrics Section*. Alexandria, VA: American Statistical Association. 59-80.
30. Sakallıoğlu, S., & Kaçiranlar, S. (2008). A new biased estimator based on ridge estimation. *Statistical Papers*, 49, 669-689.
31. Ullah, M. I., Aslam, M., and Altaf, S. (2018). Imridge: A Comprehensive R Package for Ridge Regression. *R J*, 10(2), 326.
32. Üstündağ Şiray, G., Toker, S., & Özbay, N. (2021). Defining a two-parameter estimator: a mathematical programming evidence. *Journal of Statistical Computation and Simulation*, 91(11), 2133-2152.
33. Wu, J. (2014). An Unbiased Two-Parameter Estimation with Prior Information in Linear Regression Model. *The Scientific World Journal*, 2014(1), 206943.
34. Wu, J., & Yang, H. (2013). Efficiency of an almost unbiased two-parameter estimator in linear regression model. *Statistics*, 47(3), 535-545.
35. Yang, H., and Chang, X. A new two-parameter estimator in linear regression. *Communications in Statistics-Theory and Methods*, 39(6) (2010), 923-934.
36. Zeinal, A. (2020). Generalized two-parameter estimator in linear regression model. *Journal of Mathematical Modeling*, 8(2), 157-176.